

EFFECTIVE SOCIAL FOR WEAKNESSES OF THE POPULATION ORGANIZATION AND IMPROVEMENT OF SUPPORT

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Abstract: In Uzbekistan, the principle of "Reform - not for reform, but for the benefit of the people" has been proclaimed and put into practice. To this end, special attention is paid to the implementation of a consistent and targeted state policy on social protection of citizens, support of vulnerable groups, orphans and children deprived of parental care, people with disabilities.

Key words: principle, reform, attention, special, people, parental.

ЭФФЕКТИВНАЯ СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ СЛАБЫХ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ И УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ПОДДЕРЖКИ

Аннотация: В Узбекистане провозглашен и претворен в жизнь принцип «Реформа - не ради реформы, а на благо народа». С этой целью особое внимание уделяется реализации последовательной и целенаправленной государственной политики по социальной защите граждан, поддержке уязвимых слоев населения, детей-сирот и детей, оставшихся без попечения родителей, инвалидов.

Ключевые слова: принцип, реформа, внимание, особый, народ, родительский.

INTRODUCTION

Well, first of all, "social protection" is a set of legal, economic and social measures that provide social and material protection of the country's population in the broadest sense and are determined by society; in a narrow sense - the care of the state and society for citizens in need of assistance due to age, health status, social status, inadequate means of subsistence. Its main goal is to ensure the continuous improvement of the well-being of the population, to eliminate sharp disparities in education, culture, skills, income, to help society ensure a decent standard of living and human development.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Today, about 60% of the state budget in the Republic of Uzbekistan is directed to the social sphere. Formation of a new system of health and social protection of citizens, increase the level of medical care and rehabilitation of the disabled, targeted state support of the most vulnerable and needy segments of society, providing them with specialized, high-tech medical care Comprehensive work is being done to further improve the quality of social services provided and provided. As a result of the implementation of state social programs, the health of the population has significantly improved over the past period, maternal mortality has decreased by 3.2 times and child mortality by 3.4 times. Life expectancy increases from 66 to 74 years, and among women to 76 years. In the implementation of a strong social policy in our country, along with government agencies, the funds "Mahalla", "Nuroniy", "For Healthy Generation", the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan and many other non-governmental organizations on the basis of social partnership mechanisms is operating successfully. These include sustainable and sustainable development of society and the state, improving the welfare and quality of life, strengthening family health,

protection of motherhood and childhood, expanding access to quality medical services for vulnerable groups, providing social services to citizens, including people with disabilities. improving the system, helping to provide financial support to low-income families. In order to further improve the system of social protection of vulnerable groups, to create the necessary conditions for their full participation in the socio-political life of the country, the principles of humanity, as well as the five priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 based on the tasks set out in the State Program for the implementation of the "Action Strategy" in the "Year of Active Entrepreneurship and Support of Innovative Ideas and Technologies"; Reproduction of prosthetic and orthopedic devices and technical rehabilitation aids provided free of charge by the state to persons with disabilities and introduction of their relevant standards, development of the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the rights of persons with disabilities" , providing social assistance to families living in difficult living conditions, losing a breadwinner, caring for a disabled person, using the concept of "person with a disability" instead of the concept of "disabled", identifying and preventing disability, their education assistance in obtaining and employment, establishment of modern forms and mechanisms of medical and social assistance to them ". The need to strengthen the financial resources of social protection, including the implementation of measures to improve the mechanisms of effective and targeted use of public resources and, in particular, the state budget and state trust funds, is one example of attention to the vulnerable.

Today, our country is undergoing significant socio-economic reforms and significant changes that create the conditions for the human factor to act as a decisive force and consistently develop. Our goal is to radically increase the effectiveness of reforms, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernize the country and liberalize all spheres of life. To achieve this goal, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the fourth direction, called "Development of the social sphere." These include "social protection and protection of the health of citizens and vulnerable groups; improving the quality of social assistance to the needy, raising the status of women in public life, reforming the health care system.

The government has made certain commitments on the Millennium Development Goals in order to reduce the number of low-income people in our country and to promote the further development of humanitarian principles in our society. Today, targeted measures aimed at effective social protection of the population in our country, as well as sustainable economic growth and employment provide an increase in the welfare of the population.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our country, social protection of the vulnerable and ensuring the stability of the welfare of the population, the construction of transport and communication and social infrastructure, support for mines with unfavorable environmental conditions, social protection of the population and the creation of new jobs. tibor focused. In recent years, Uzbekistan has become a logical continuation of the process of renewal and deepening reforms in our society, a new and high stage in our work to strengthen social protection and improve the living standards of our people by strengthening the potential, stability and balance of our economy. During this period, the social policy in the field of social protection in the country was implemented in the following areas:

1. Focus social benefits on low-income families;
2. Ensuring addressability in social protection;

3. To this end, gradually improve the mechanisms for ensuring the delivery of benefits to low-income families through the community;

4. Attraction of funds for sponsorship, charitable organizations, enterprises, along with public financial sources for social protection of the population.

In the first difficult years of independence, in order to stabilize the living standards of the people in our country, many methods and means of state management of the process of social support, protection of social spheres, provision of social guarantees were used. In particular, the salaries, pensions, stipends, allowances have been gradually increased, direct cash payments in the form of compensation payments, benefits and various subsidies have been introduced, differences in the prices of socially important goods and services have been budgeted. methods such as reimbursement, allocation of benefits to different needy segments of the population, ensuring that they are targeted, the development of a package of state-guaranteed social services and its full funding have been widely used. In order to provide social support to vulnerable groups of the population, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Resolution No. 350 of December 12, 2012 "On measures to further improve the procedure for the appointment and payment of social benefits." The decision was made "in order to strengthen the specific social assistance to families with minor children and low-income families," according to which from January 1, 2013, there will be no minors (under 14). monthly benefits to families in the amount of 50, 80 and 100 percent of the minimum wage set at the beginning of the year, depending on the number of children, benefits to mothers with children under 2 years of age in the amount of 2 times the minimum wage, low-income families for which the allowance was set at 1.5-3 times the minimum wage.

CONCLUSION

In recent years, much attention has been paid to improving the living standards of the population. A number of government decisions and regulations aimed at their implementation have been adopted.

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